

TECHNOLOGY OF IMPROVING GENERAL COMPETENCE OF ADOLESCENT GIRLS THROUGH NATIONAL CRAFT

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Abstract. *In this article, the technology of improving general professional competence of adolescent girls by means of national handicrafts, organizational, methodical and reflexive organization of pedagogical activity, having a pure-based concept to achieve its effectiveness, training of adolescent girls in national. The methods of creating the concept of improving general professional competence by means of crafts are explained.*

Key words: *national crafts, teenage girls, competence, concept, "Morphological analysis", "Clustering" ("Cluster analysis"), "Designing" methods, "Perceptual mapping" technology.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the important directions of human capital creation in Uzbekistan is the professional socialization of youth, which is recognized as the main factor, and special attention is paid to the ways, content, means and methods of targeted orientation of youth to professions. In particular, the problem of educating adolescents on the basis of national values, developing their hard work skills, has acquired a developmental character, and in this regard, the resources created by such thinkers as Abu Ali ibn Sino, Abu Nasr Farobi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Amir Temur, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Kaykovus are of great importance in vocational education.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

At the current stage of Uzbekistan's development, the research works of local pedagogical scientists M. Kuronov, O. Musurmonova, S. Turgunov, N. Egamberdiyeva, M. Artikova, S. Bulatov and others have scientifically interpreted the issues of choosing a profession and a value-based approach to it, developed scientific conclusions and methodological recommendations on improving the social activity of young people based on the requirements of the time

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Today, the main goal of education in our republic is to educate young people as well-rounded individuals, while providing employment for girls who are reaching adulthood, and directing them to a profession so that they can find their place in life have become urgent tasks of our government's policy. Especially, directing teenage girls (12-15) to national crafts, based on their interests, abilities, skills and opportunities, is one of the problems that is waiting for its solution. Attention was paid to improving the general professional competencies of teenage girls, their ability to adapt to working conditions: the ability to choose raw materials and materials; visual perception; emotional and practical approach to work; ability to develop self-professional development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Organizing pedagogical activities that promote the goal of directing teenage girls to a profession, developing in them primary professional knowledge, skills and qualifications, experience and their combination of competencies, is not simply a matter of setting up. Perhaps,

it is necessary to organize a conceptually well-thought-out, rationally constructed implementation mechanism in accordance with a strategic approach.

In this process, it is important to take into account that the professional competencies possessed by a teenage girl are reflected in the knowledge, skills, qualifications and experience that help teenage girls effectively solve certain professional tasks. Improving the general professional competence of teenage girls through national crafts is a specific goal-oriented, complex, multi-stage pedagogical process. Taking into account the specific aspects of this process, an integrated approach to its organization is required. This is due to the fact that during the research, pedagogical activities are organized in several national crafts at the same time, based on the interests, needs and motivations of teenage girls. The correct organizational, methodological and reflexive organization of pedagogical activity, the presence of a well-founded concept for achieving its effectiveness is considered the basis for ensuring the success of scientific and pedagogical research.

The concept of improving general professional competence through national crafts is a system of basic views that determines the strategy of action aimed at developing general professional competence in a particular individual by directing them to professional activities in national crafts, and adolescent girls were taken as the object of the formation of this system within the framework of the study. When developing and substantiating a specific concept, interested parties are identified. Family, neighborhood, educational institutions and society are considered interested parties in the process of improving the general professional competence of adolescent girls through national crafts. The concept aims to provide vocational guidance to adolescent girls by building on their acquired general professional competencies, consisting of knowledge, skills, qualifications, and experience in the field, based on the specific characteristics of selected national crafts.

The socio-economic adaptation of adolescent girls to the relations established in the system based on market production, their resistance to strong competition in the labor market, and their achievement of financial and economic independence indicate that they have developed general professional competencies through national crafts. The field of national crafts combines a range of socio-pedagogical opportunities. In particular, they mature in a certain type of industry; acquire such qualities as worldview, aesthetic taste, creativity, self-awareness, confidence in their own strength and capabilities, financial and economic independence, and adaptation to the market economy; contribute to the formation of the family budget in the future; contribute to the preservation of centuries-old national values, their transmission to future generations; apply modern approaches to the process of creating national crafts; achieve a harmonious combination of national and modernity in the image of the created product.

In the process of making national handicrafts, teenage girls also learn honesty, purity, responsibility for the quality of their actions and the product of their labor, loyalty (the ability to fulfill a promise), and mutual respect between teacher and student. The relevance of improving general professional competencies in teenage girls through national handicrafts is determined by the purposeful development of human capital, as well as the effective orientation of the individual to professional activity, filling the production market, satisfying the needs of the population, especially tourists, for national handicraft products, creating the necessary conditions for employment of citizens, reducing poverty, and creating a source of financial and economic income.

The concept of improving general professional competencies of teenage girls through national handicrafts is created using specific methods. When conducting research, attention is paid

to the selection of innovative methods and technologies to effectively organize the process and achieve productive results. As a result, the following methods are considered to be of high importance in achieving the expected result:

I. Effective methods:

1. Morphological analysis method
2. Clustering method
3. Design method

II. Innovative technology: “Perceptual map” technology (prepared using the Coggle.it online service).

I. Effective methods:

“Morphological analysis” method. Also known as “Morphological box”. “For almost a century, the “Morphological Box” graphic organizer has been a method based on analyzing the structural structure of an object, which involves systematizing all options that represent the theoretical possibilities of the decision being made. As is known, things are usually placed in boxes in a certain order. If the box is quite voluminous, several types of things, items or equipment are placed in it separately, depending on the type. That is, a certain place is allocated to things in the box according to their type. The didactic value of this method, which serves to study problem situations and select solutions, is that it allows you to consider each case that illuminates the general essence of a particular process, type, or even area. This method, which is analytical in nature by its content, also helps to clarify ideas about the system and its structural foundations.”

Clustering (cluster analysis) method. This method is a method that “creates several relatively small groups based on the hierarchical grouping of objects”, “a method that divides objects into clusters (groups) based on their meaning, thematic proximity, mutual equality of stakeholders, and the ability to meet the official requirements”, which “serves to combine many objects separated by certain criteria into several parts (clusters). Each cluster includes objects that are as similar as possible to itself. It is possible to perform clustering within the cluster itself again, that is, to create several more small clusters. This action helps to form a holistic hierarchical structure consisting of clusters that are compatible with each other, from small to large.”

Project method. To fully understand the essence of this method, it is worth finding out what the concept of “project” is used for. The concept of “project” (lat. “projectus”; ling. “design” – “proposed in advance”; “planned”; “visible”) is “a product of action aimed at developing the content of pedagogical activity, based on a clear plan, goal, guaranteeing its results”; a person’s “organized actions to solve a specific problem, methods used by him, which are set in a certain sequence – tasks that are significant for him and are recorded as a product that has been achieved in some way”.

I. Innovative technology: “Perceptual mapping” technology (prepared using the Coggle.it online service). 1974 – The “Perceptual mapping” technology, founded by Tony Buzan, is considered a technology that, according to its essential and important features, “serves to visualize information in order to group information in a certain order and find relationships between them” and “provides a natural visual representation of a system of thoughts based on the main idea”. The technology is also known as “Mental Map”, “Intellect Map”.

The “Perception Map” (or “Mental Map”) technology “serves to develop the ability to systematize basic concepts on a relevant topic and group them according to certain characteristics, essence”. “At first glance, this method resembles the “Cluster” graphic organizer. However, the

most important difference between them is that the basic concepts are represented using clusters or direction lines (“branches”; lines that determine the direction of the map”).

CONCLUSION

The process of developing general professional competencies of adolescent girls in national crafts, ensuring the social subject's employment, eliminating underemployment and poverty, establishing family entrepreneurship, fully realizing their creative potential, and creating experience in demonstrating their ability to enter not only the local but also the international labor market, has been improved based on the substantiation of an indicator assessing the ability to work with the methods of "Morphological Analysis", "Clustering" ("Cluster Analysis"), "Projection" and the "Perception Map" technology.

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